

Microcontroller 8051

MMC

MICROPROCESSORS AND MICROCONTROLLERS

<i>Microprocessor</i>	<i>Microcontroller</i>
<i>Block diagram of microprocessor</i>	<i>Block diagram of microcontroller</i>
Microprocessor contains ALU, General purpose registers, stack pointer, program counter, clock timing circuit, interrupt circuit	Microcontroller contains the circuitry of microprocessor, and in addition it has built in ROM, RAM, I/O Devices, Timers/Counters etc.
It has many instructions to move data between memory and CPU	It has few instructions to move data between memory and CPU
Few bit handling instruction	It has many bit handling instructions
Less number of pins are multifunctional	More number of pins are multifunctional
Single memory map for data and code (program)	Separate memory map for data and code (program)
Access time for memory and IO are more	Less access time for built in memory and IO.
Microprocessor based system requires additional hardware	It requires less additional hardwares
More flexible in the design point of view	Less flexible since the additional circuits which is residing inside the microcontroller is fixed for a particular microcontroller
Large number of instructions with flexible addressing modes	Limited number of instructions with few addressing modes

Types of microcontrollers

RISC AND CISC CPU ARCHITECTURES

RISC	CISC
Instruction takes one or two cycles	Instruction takes multiple cycles
Only load/store instructions are used to access memory	In additions to load and store instructions, memory access is possible with other instructions also.
Instructions executed by hardware	Instructions executed by the micro program
Fixed format instruction	Variable format instructions
Few addressing modes	Many addressing modes
Few instructions	Complex instruction set
Most of the have multiple register banks	Single register bank
Highly pipelined	Less pipelined
Complexity is in the compiler	Complexity in the microprogram

HARVARD & VON- NEUMANN CPU ARCHITECTURE

Von-Neumann (Princeton architecture)	Harvard architecture
<p>The diagram shows a CPU on the left connected to two separate buses. The top bus is labeled 'Data' and connects to 'Data Memory'. The bottom bus is labeled 'Address Bus' and connects to 'Program Memory'.</p>	
Von-Neumann (Princeton architecture)	Harvard architecture
It uses single memory space for both instructions and data.	It has separate program memory and data memory
It is not possible to fetch instruction code and data	Instruction code and data can be fetched simultaneously
Execution of instruction takes more machine cycle	Execution of instruction takes less machine cycle
Uses CISC architecture	Uses RISC architecture
Instruction pre-fetching is a main feature	Instruction parallelism is a main feature
Also known as control flow or control driven computers	Also known as data flow or data driven computers
Simplifies the chip design because of single memory space	Chip design is complex due to separate memory space
Eg. 8085, 8086, MC6800	Eg. General purpose microcontrollers, special DSP chips etc.

Salient features of 8051 Microcontroller

- Eight bit CPU
- 4Kbytes of internal program memory (code memory) *[ROM]*
- 128 bytes of internal data memory *[RAM]*
- 64 Kbytes of external program memory address space.
- 64 Kbytes of external data memory address space.
- 32 bi directional I/O lines (can be used as four 8 bit ports or 32 individually addressable I/O lines)
- Two 16 Bit Timer/Counter :T₀, T₁
- Full Duplex serial data receiver/transmitter
- Four Register banks with 8 registers in each bank.
- Sixteen bit Program counter (PC) and a data pointer (DPTR)

Salient features of 8051 Microcontroller

- 8 Bit Stack Pointer
- Five vector interrupt structure (RESET not considered as an interrupt.)
- 8051 CPU consists of 8 bit ALU with associated registers like accumulator 'A', B register,
- 16 bit program counter and DPTR.
- ALU can perform arithmetic and logic functions on 8 bit variables.
- 8051 has 128 bytes of internal RAM which is divided into
 - Working registers [00 – 1F]
 - Bit addressable memory area [20 – 2F]
 - General purpose memory area (Scratch pad memory) [30-7F]
- 8051 has 4 K Bytes of internal ROM. The address space is from 0000 to 0FFFh. If the program size is more than 4 K Bytes 8051 will fetch the code automatically from external memory.

Salient features of 8051 Microcontroller

- Accumulator is an 8 bit register widely used for all arithmetic and logical operations. Accumulator is also used to transfer data between external memory. B register is used along with Accumulator for multiplication and division. A and B registers together is also called MATH registers.
- Stack Pointer (SP) – it contains the address of the data item on the top of the stack. Stack may reside anywhere on the internal RAM. On reset, SP is initialized to 07 so that the default stack will start from address 08 onwards.
- Data Pointer (DPTR) – DPH (Data pointer higher byte), DPL (Data pointer lower byte). This is a 16 bit register which is used to furnish address information for internal and external program memory and for external data memory.
- Program Counter (PC) – 16 bit PC contains the address of next instruction to be executed. On reset PC will set to 0000H. After fetching every instruction PC will increment by one.

8051 Flag bits and the PSW register

- PSW Register

CY	AC	Fo	RS1	RS0	OV	--	P
----	----	----	-----	-----	----	----	---

<i>Carry flag</i>	PSW.7	CY
<i>Auxiliary carry flag</i>	PSW.6	AC
<i>Available to the user for general purpose</i>	PSW.5	--
<i>Register Bank selector bit 1</i>	PSW.4	RS1
<i>Register Bank selector bit 0</i>	PSW.3	RS0
<i>Overflow flag</i>	PSW.2	OV
<i>User define bit</i>	PSW.1	--
<i>Parity flag Set/Reset odd/even parity</i>	PSW.0	P

RS1	RS0	Register Bank	Address
0	0	0	00H-07H
0	1	1	08H-0FH
1	0	2	10H-17H
1	1	3	18H-1FH

Memory Organization

- RAM memory space allocation in the 8051

Registers

Some 8-bit Registers of
the 8051

Some 8051 16-bit Register

Architecture of 8051

8051 Internal Block Diagram

Pin Description of the 8051

Pins of 8051 (1/4)

- Vcc (pin 40) :
 - Vcc provides supply voltage to the chip.
 - The voltage source is +5V.
- GND (pin 20) : ground
- XTAL1 and XTAL2 (pins 19,18) :
 - These 2 pins provide external clock.

Pins of 8051 (2/4)

- RST (pin 9) : reset
 - It is an input pin and is active high (normally low) .
 - The high pulse must be high at least 2 machine cycles.
 - It is a power-on reset.
 - Upon applying a high pulse to RST, the microcontroller will reset and all values in registers will be lost.

8051 Reset Circuit

(1)

(2)

(1) Power-on Reset Circuit and (2) With Manual Reset Option

Power-On RESET Circuit

RESET Value of Some 8051 Registers:

Register	Reset Value
PC	0000
ACC	0000
B	0000
PSW	0000
SP	0007
DPTR	0000

Pins of 8051 (3/4)

- $\overline{\text{EA}}$ (pin 31) : external access
 - There is no on-chip ROM in 8031 and 8032 .
 - The $\overline{\text{EA}}$ pin is connected to GND to indicate the code is stored externally.
 - $\overline{\text{PSEN}}$ & ALE are used for external ROM.
 - For 8051, $\overline{\text{EA}}$ pin is connected to Vcc.
 - “ $\overline{\text{}}$ ” means active low.
- $\overline{\text{PSEN}}$ (pin 29) : program store enable
 - This is an output pin and is connected to the OE pin of the ROM.

Pins of 8051 (4/4)

- ALE (pin 30) : address latch enable
 - It is an output pin and is active high.
 - 8051 port 0 provides both address and data.
 - The ALE pin is used for de-multiplexing the address and data by connecting to the G pin of the 74LS373 latch.
- I/O port pins
 - The four ports P0, P1, P2, and P3.
 - Each port uses 8 pins.
 - All I/O pins are bi-directional.

Pins of I/O Port

- The 8051 has four I/O ports
 - Port 0 (pins 32-39) : P0 (P0.0 ~ P0.7)
 - Port 1 (pins 1-8) : P1 (P1.0 ~ P1.7)
 - Port 2 (pins 21-28) : P2 (P2.0 ~ P2.7)
 - Port 3 (pins 10-17) : P3 (P3.0 ~ P3.7)
 - Each port has **8 pins**.
 - Named P0.X (X=0,1,...,7) , P1.X, P2.X, P3.X
 - Ex : P0.0 is the bit 0 (LSB) of P0
 - Ex : P0.7 is the bit 7 (MSB) of P0
 - These 8 bits form a byte.
- Each port can be used as input or output (bi-direction).

Instruction Timing

- One “machine cycle” = 6 states (S1 - S6)
- One state = 2 clock cycles
 - One “machine cycle” = 12 clock cycles
- Instructions take 1 - 4 cycles
 - e.g. 1 cycle instructions: ADD, MOV, SETB, NOP
 - e.g. 2 cycle instructions: JMP, JZ
 - 4 cycle instructions: MUL, DIV

8051 machine cycle

CPU timing

- Most 8051 instructions are executed in one cycle.
- MUL (multiply) and DIV (divide) are the only instructions that take more than two cycles to complete (four cycles)
- Normally two code bytes are fetched from the program memory during every machine cycle.
- The only exception to this is when a MOVX instruction is executed. MOVX is a one-byte, 2-cycle instruction that accesses external data memory.
- During a MOVX, the two fetches in the second cycle are skipped while the external data memory is being addressed and strobed.

Example :

Find the machine cycle for

(a) XTAL = 11.0592 MHz

(b) XTAL = 16 MHz.

Solution:

(a) $11.0592 \text{ MHz} / 12 = 921.6 \text{ kHz}$;

machine cycle = $1 / 921.6 \text{ kHz} = 1.085 \mu\text{s}$

(b) $16 \text{ MHz} / 12 = 1.333 \text{ MHz}$;

machine cycle = $1 / 1.333 \text{ MHz} = 0.75 \mu\text{s}$

The 8051 Assembly Language

Overview

- Data transfer instructions
- Data processing
 - Arithmetic Instructions
 - Logical Instructions
- Program flow instructions

Data Transfer Instructions

- MOV
- MOVX
- MOVC
- PUSH
- POP
- XCH

Addressing Modes

Immediate Mode – specify data by its **value**

```
mov A, #0           ;put 0 in the accumulator
                    ;A = 00000000

mov R4, #11h        ;put 11hex in the R4 register
                    ;R4 = 00010001

mov B, #11          ;put 11 decimal in b register
                    ;B = 00001011

mov DPTR, #7521h    ;put 7521 hex in DPTR
                    ;DPTR = 0111010100100001
```

Addressing Modes

Register Addressing – either source or destination is one of CPU register (R0-R7,A,DPTR)

```
MOV R0 , A
```

```
MOV A , R7
```

```
ADD A , R4
```

```
ADD A , R7
```

```
MOV DPTR , #25F5H
```

```
MOV R5 , DPL
```

```
MOV R2 , DPH
```

Note that MOV R4 , R7 is incorrect

Addressing Modes

Direct Mode – specify data by its 8-bit address , usually for 30h-7Fh of RAM (128 BYTES RAM, SFRs)

Mov a , 70h

Mov 50h , #50h

Mov 56h , a

Mov 0D0h , a

Mov 40h , R4

Mov R0 , 40h

Mov 40h , 50H

Addressing Modes

Direct Mode – Using R0-R7 in direct addressing

MOV A, 4 ≡ MOV A, R4

MOV A, 7 ≡ MOV A, R7

MOV 7, 2 ≡ ~~MOV R7, R6~~

MOV R2, #5 ; Put 5 in R2

MOV R2, 5 ; Put content of RAM at 5 in R2

Addressing Modes

Register Indirect – the address of the source or destination is specified in registers

Uses registers R0 or R1 for **8-bit** address:

```
mov psw, #00           ; use register bank 0
mov r0, #3CH
mov @r0, #03           ; memory at 3C gets #3
                       ; M[3C] ← 3
```

Uses DPTR register for **16-bit** addresses:

```
mov dptr, #9000H       ; dptr ← 9000h
movx a, @dptr          ; a ← M[9000]
```

Note that 9000 is an address in external memory

Addressing Modes

- Register Indirect

- Mov @Ro,#20h

- Mov @R1,20h

- Mov 20h,@Ro

- Mov a,@R1

- Mov @R1,a

- The number in Ro or R1 must be in RAM.

External Data Moves

MOVX is used with external RAM or I/O addresses (R₀, R₁, DPTR)

- Movx a,@Rp
- Movx a,@DPTR
- Movx @Rp, a
- Movx @DPTR,a

MOVC is used to move data from source address in the code ROM to Accumulator

- Movc a, @a+DPTR
- Movc a, @a+PC

PUSH and POP

- PUSH add
- POP add
- add= 00h to FFh

These opcodes specify direct address of the data.

Used to access stack memory area, pointed by SP.

Stacks

Stack

- Stack-oriented data transfer
 - Only one operand (**direct** addressing)
 - SP is other operand – register indirect - implied
- Direct addressing mode must be used in Push and Pop

```
mov sp, #0x40    ; Initialize SP
push 55h         ; SP ← SP+1, M[SP] ← M[55]
                 ; M[41] ← M[55]
pop 42h          ; M[42] ← M[41], SP ← SP-1
```

Note: can only specify RAM or SFRs (direct mode) to push or pop.
Therefore, to push/pop the accumulator, must use **address**, not **a**

Exchange Instructions

- XCH a, R0
- XCH a, 40h
- XCH a, @R1
- XCHD a, @R0

Exchange Instructions

two way data transfer

```
XCH a, 30h ; a  $\leftrightarrow$  M[30]  
XCH a, R0 ; a  $\leftrightarrow$  R0  
XCH a, @R0 ; a  $\leftrightarrow$  M[R0]  
XCHD a, @R0 ; exchange "digit"
```


Data Processing Instructions

Arithmetic Instructions

Logic Instructions

Arithmetic Instructions

- Add
- Subtract
- Increment
- Decrement
- Multiply
- Divide
- Decimal adjust

Arithmetic Instructions

- ADD A, #30h
- ADD A, R2
- ADD A, 30h
- ADD A, @R1

Arithmetic Instructions

- ADDC A, #30h
- ADDC A, R₂
- ADDC A, 30h
- ADDC A, @R₁

ADD Instructions

add a, byte ; $a \leftarrow a + \text{byte}$

addc a, byte ; $a \leftarrow a + \text{byte} + C$

These instructions affect 3 bits in PSW:

$C = 1$ if result of add is greater than FF

$AC = 1$ if there is a carry out of bit 3

$OV = 1$ if there is a carry out of bit 7, but not from bit 6, or visa versa.

Program Status Word (PSW)

Bit	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	0
Flag	CY	AC	F0	RS1	RS0	OV	F1	P
Name	Carry Flag	Auxiliary Carry Flag	User Flag 0	Register Bank Select 1	Register Bank Select 0	Overflow flag	User Flag 1	Parity Bit

ADD Examples

```
mov a, #3Fh  
add a, #0D3h
```

```
0011 1111  
1101 0011  
          
0001 0010
```

C = 1

AC = 1

OV = 0

- What is the value of the C, AC, OV flags after the second instruction is executed?

Subtract

<code>SUBB A, byte</code>	subtract with borrow
---------------------------	----------------------

Example:

```
SUBB A, #4Fh      ;A ← A - 4F - C
```

Notice that

There is **no** subtraction **WITHOUT** borrow.

Therefore, if a subtraction without borrow is desired, it is necessary to **clear the C** flag.

Example:

```
Clr  c
```

```
SUBB A, #4Fh      ;A ← A - 4F
```

Arithmetic Instructions

- SUBB A, #30h
- SUBB A, R2
- SUBB A, 30h
- SUBB A, @R1

Increment and Decrement

INC A	increment A
INC byte	increment byte in memory
INC DPTR	increment data pointer
DEC A	decrement accumulator
DEC byte	decrement byte

- The increment and decrement instructions do **NOT** affect the C flag.
- Notice we can **only** INCREMENT the data pointer, not decrement.

Increment and Decrement

- INC A
- INC 50
- INC R6
- INC @R1
- INC DPTR

- DEC A
- DEC 50
- DEC R5
- DEC @R1

Example: Increment 16-bit Word

- Assume 16-bit word in R3:R2

```
mov a, r2
```

```
add a, #01          ; use add rather than increment to affect C
```

```
mov r2, a
```

```
mov a, r3
```

```
addc a, #00        ; add C to most significant byte
```

```
mov r3, a
```

Multiply

When multiplying two 8-bit numbers, the size of the maximum product is 16-bits

$$FF \times FF = FE01$$

$$(255 \times 255 = 65025)$$

MUL AB ; BA ← A * B

Note : B gets the High byte
A gets the Low byte

Division

- Division

DIV AB ; divide A by B

A ← Quotient (A/B)

B ← Remainder (A/B)

OV - used to indicate a divide by zero condition.

C - set to zero

Decimal Adjust

DA a ; decimal adjust a

Used to facilitate BCD addition.

Adds “6” to either high or low nibble after an addition to create a valid BCD number.

Example:

```
mov a, #23h
```

```
mov b, #29h
```

```
add a, b
```

```
; a ← 23h + 29h = 4Ch (wanted 52)
```

```
DA a
```

```
; a ← a + 6 = 52
```

Arithmetic Instructions

Mnemonic	Description
ADD A, byte	add A to byte(#n, R, Add, @R), put result in A
ADDC A, byte	add with carry
SUBB A, byte	subtract with borrow
INC A	increment A
INC byte	increment byte in memory (Direct or Indirect)
INC DPTR	increment data pointer
DEC A	decrement accumulator
DEC byte	decrement byte in memory (Direct or Indirect)
MUL AB	multiply accumulator by b register
DIV AB	divide accumulator by b register
DA A	decimal adjust the accumulator

Logical Instructions

- ❑ Byte-level logical Instructions
- ❑ Bit level logical Instructions

ANL → AND

ORL → OR

XRL → XOR

CPL → Complement

Byte Level Logical Instructions

- ANL A,#50
- ANL A,50H
- ANL A,@R0
- ANL A,R7
- ANL 50,A
- ANL 30,#20h

Byte Level Logical Instructions

- ORL A,#50
- ORL A,50H
- ORL A,@R0
- ORL A,R7
- ORL 50,A
- ORL 30,#20h

Byte Level Logical Instructions

- XRL A,#50
- XRL A,50H
- XRL A,@R0
- XRL A,R7
- XRL 50,A
- XRL 30,#20h

BIT-ORIENTED (SOURCES) BIT ADDRESSABLE RAM

RAM

Byte address	Bit address							
27	3F	3E	3D	3C	3B	3A	39	38
26	37	36	35	34	33	32	31	30
25	2F	2E	2D	2C	2B	2A	29	28
24	27	26	25	24	23	22	21	20
23	1F	1E	1D	1C	1B	1A	19	18
22	17	16	15	14	13	12	11	10
21	0F	0E	0D	0C	0B	0A	09	08
20	07	06	05	04	03	02	01	00
1F	Bank 3							
18								
17	Bank 2							
10								
0F								
08	Bank 1							
07								
00								
Default register bank for R0–R7								

Bit-addressable locations

Byte address

Byte address	Bit address															
7F	General purpose RAM															
30																
2F									7F	7E	7D	7C	7B	7A	79	78
2E									77	76	75	74	73	72	71	70
2D									6F	6E	6D	6C	6B	6A	69	68
2C									67	66	65	64	63	62	61	60
2B									5F	5E	5D	5C	5B	5A	59	58
2A									57	56	55	54	53	52	51	50
29									4F	4E	4D	4C	4B	4A	49	48
28									47	46	45	44	43	42	41	40

Bit-addressable locations

BIT-ORIENTED (SOURCES) BIT ADDRESSABLE SFRs

Byte address	Bit address		Byte address	Bit address	
98	9F 9E 9D 9C 9B 9A 99 98	SCON	FF		
			F0	F7 F6 F5 F4 F3 F2 F1 F0	B
90	97 96 95 94 93 92 91 90	PI			
			E0	E7 E6 E5 E4 E3 E2 E1 E0	ACC
8D	not bit addressable	TH1			
8C	not bit addressable	TH0	D0	D7 D6 D5 D4 D3 D2 - D0	PSW
8B	not bit addressable	TL1			
8A	not bit addressable	TL0	B8	- - - BC BB BA B9 B8	IP
89	not bit addressable	TMOD			
88	8F 8E 8D 8C 8B 8A 89 88	TCON	B0	B7 B6 B5 B4 B3 B2 B1 B0	P3
87	not bit addressable	PCON			
			A8	AF - - AC AB AA A9 A8	IE
83	not bit addressable	DPH			
82	not bit addressable	DPL	A0	A7 A6 A5 A4 A3 A2 A1 A0	P2
81	not bit addressable	SP			
80	87 86 85 84 83 82 81 80	P0	99	not bit addressable	SBUF

EXAMPLES

- SFRs with addresses ending in 0 or 8 are bit-addressable.
(80, 88, 90, 98, etc)
- Notice that all 4 parallel I/O ports are bit addressable.
- Force individual bits low, without affecting other bits.

```
anl PSW, #0E7 ;PSW AND 11100111
```

- Force individual bits high.

```
orl PSW, #18 ;PSW OR 00011000
```

- Complement individual bits

```
xrl P1, #40 ;P1 XRL 01000000
```

Bit-Oriented Data Transfer

- Transfers between individual bits.
- Carry flag (C) (bit 7 in the PSW) is used as a single-bit accumulator
- RAM bits in addresses 20-2F are bit addressable

```
mov C, P0.0
```

```
mov C, 67h
```

```
mov C, 2c.7
```


Bit Logic Operations

- Some logic operations can be used with single bit operands

```
ANL C, bit
ANL C, /bit
ORL C, bit
ORL C, /bit
CLR C
CLR bit
CPL C
CPL bit
SETB C
SETB bit
```

- “bit” can be any of the bit-addressable RAM locations or SFRs.

Other Logic Instructions

CLR - clear

RL - rotate left

RLC - rotate left through Carry

RR - rotate right

RRC - rotate right through Carry

SWAP - swap accumulator nibbles

CLR and CPL

CLR A

CPL A

No CLR command for other addressing modes

Rotate

- Rotate instructions operate **only** on **a**

RL a

Mov a, #0xF0 ; a ← 11110000

RL a ; a ← 11100001

RR a

Mov a, #0xF0 ; a ← 11110000

RR a ; a ← 01111000

Rotate through Carry

RRC a


```
mov a, #0A9h      ; a ← A9  
add a, #14h      ; a ← BD (10111101), C←0  
rrc a            ; a ← 01011110, C←1
```

RLC a


```
mov a, #3ch      ; a ← 3ch (00111100)  
setb c          ; c ← 1  
rlc a           ; a ← 01111001, C←1
```

Rotate and Multiplication/Division

- Note that a shift left is the same as multiplying by 2, shift right is divide by 2

```
mov a, #3      ; A ← 00000011 (3)
clr C          ; C ← 0
rlc a         ; A ← 00000110 (6)
rlc a         ; A ← 00001100 (12)
rrc a         ; A ← 00000110 (6)
```

Swap

SWAP a


```
mov a, #72h
```

```
; a ← 72h
```

```
swap a
```

```
; a ← 27h
```

Instructions that Affect PSW bits

Instructions that Affect Flag Settings⁽¹⁾

Instruction	Flag			Instruction	Flag		
	C	OV	AC		C	OV	AC
ADD	X	X	X	CLR C	0		
ADDC	X	X	X	CPL C	X		
SUBB	X	X	X	ANL C,bit	X		
MUL	0	X		ANL C,/bit	X		
DIV	0	X		ORL C,bit	X		
DA	X			ORL C,/bit	X		
RRC	X			MOV C,bit	X		
RLC	X			CJNE	X		
SETB C	1						

Program Flow Control

Classification of Branch Control Instructions

- Unconditional jumps (“go to”)
- Conditional jumps
- Call and return

Unconditional Jumps

- **SJMP <rel addr>** ; Short jump, relative address is 8-bit 2's complement number, so jump can be up to 127 locations forward, or 128 locations back.
- **LJMP <address 16>** ; Long jump, address is 16-bit, so jump location can be located anywhere within 64K memory (0000h -FFFFh).
- **AJMP <address 11>** ; Absolute jump to anywhere within 2K block of program memory
- **JMP @A + DPTR** ; Long indexed jump

Infinite Loops


```
Start: mov C, p3.7  
      mov p1.6, C  
      sjmp Start
```

SJMP

- It is jump to location within -128 bytes to +127 from current location.
- Example

```
Full step anticlockwise
9000      Main:  MOV P1,#09h      75      90      03
9003      ACALL Delay          11      16
9005      MOV P1,#0Ch          75      90      06
9008      ACALL Delay          11      16
900A      MOV P1,#06h          75      90      0C
900D      ACALL Delay          11      16
900F      MOV P1,#03H          75      90      09
9012      ACALL Delay          11      16
9014      SJMP Main           80      EA
```

Jump Address Calculation.

Line	PC	Opcode		Mnemonic	Operand
01	0000			ORG	0000
02	0000	7800		MOV	R0,#0
03	0002	7455		MOV	A,#55H
04	0004	6003		JZ	NEXT
05	0006	08		INC	R0
06	0007	04	AGAIN:	INC	A
07	0008	04		INC	A
08	0009	2477	NEXT:	ADD	A,#77h
09	000B	5005		JNC	OVER
10	000D	E4		CLR	A
11	000E	F8		MOV	R0,A
12	000F	F9		MOV	R1,A
13	0010	FA		MOV	R2,A
14	0011	FB		MOV	R3,A
15	0012	2B	OVER:	ADD	A,R3
16	0013	50F2		JNC	AGAIN
17	0015	80FE	HERE:	SJMP	HERE
18	0017			END	

AJMP: Absolute Jump

- It makes use of concept of dividing memory into logical divisions called pages.
- Program memory is logically arranged as 2K pages, giving total of 32 (20h) pages.

- The **AJMP** instruction transfers program execution to the specified address. The address is formed by combining the 5 high-order bits of the address of the following instruction (for A15-A11), the 3 high-order bits of the opcode (for A10-A8), and the second byte of the instruction (for A7-A0). The destination address must be located in the same 2KByte block of program memory as the opcode following the **AJMP** instruction. No flags are affected.

- **AJMP** $A_{10}A_9A_800001A_7A_6A_5A_4A_3A_2A_1A_0$

- **Operation** $PC_{10-0} = A_{10-0}$

- **Example** **AJMP LABEL**

Re-locatable Code

Memory specific NOT Re-locatable (machine code)

```
org 8000h  
Start: mov C, p1.6  
      mov p3.7, C  
      ljmp Start  
      end
```

Re-locatable (machine code)

```
org 8000h  
Start: mov C, p1.6  
      mov p3.7, C  
      sjmp Start  
      end
```

Comparison

SJMP	LJMP	AJMP
Short jump, relative address is 8 bit it support 127 location forward	Long jump range is 64 kb	Absolute jump to anywhere within 2k block of program memory
It uses 8 bit address.	It uses 16 bit address	It uses an 11 bit address
2 byte instruction.	3 byte instruction	2 byte instruction
Conditional branch instruction can use,relative JMP.	Cannot use long JMP	Cannot the JMP absolute
Address calculation	PC is equal to 11 bit	PC is equal to 16 bit.

Conditional Jump

- These instructions cause a jump to occur **only** if a condition is **true**. Otherwise, program execution continues with the next instruction.

```
loop: mov a, P1
      jz  loop      ; if a=0, goto loop,
                   ; else goto next instruction
      mov b, a
```

- There is **no** zero flag (**z**)
- Content of A checked for zero **on time**

Example: Conditional Jumps

```
if (a = 0) is true
    send a 0 to LED
else
    send a 1 to LED
```

```
                jz led_off
                Setb P1.6
                sjmp skipover
led_off:        clr P1.6
                mov A, P0
skipover:
```

Conditional jumps

Mnemonic	Description
JZ <rel addr>	Jump if a = 0
JNZ <rel addr>	Jump if a != 0
JC <rel addr>	Jump if C = 1
JNC <rel addr>	Jump if C != 1
JB <bit>, <rel addr>	Jump if bit = 1
JNB <bit>,<rel addr>	Jump if bit != 1
JBC <bit>, <rel addr>	Jump if bit =1, &clear bit
CJNE A, direct, <rel addr>	Compare A and memory, jump if not equal

More Conditional Jumps

Mnemonic	Description
CJNE A, #data <rel addr>	Compare A and data, jump if not equal
CJNE Rn, #data <rel addr>	Compare Rn and data, jump if not equal
CJNE @Rn, #data <rel addr>	Compare Rn and memory, jump if not equal
DJNZ Rn, <rel addr>	Decrement Rn and then jump if not zero
DJNZ direct, <rel addr>	Decrement memory and then jump if not zero

Iterative Loops(examples)

```
    mov a,#50h
    mov b,#00h
    cjne a,#50h,next
    mov  b,#01h
next: nop
    end
```

```
    mov a,#0aah
    mov b,#10h
Back1:mov r6,#50
Back2:cpl a
      djnz r6,back2
      djnz b,back1
    end
```

```
    mov a,#25h
    mov r0,#10h
    mov r2,#5
Again: mov @ro,a
      inc r0
      djnz r2,again
    end
```

```
    mov a,#0h
    mov r4,#12h
Back:  add a,#05
      djnz r4,back
    mov  r5,a
    end
```

Call and Return

- Call is similar to a jump, but
 - Call **pushes PC** on stack before branching

```
acall <address 11>      ; stack ← PC  
                          ; PC ← address 11 bit
```

```
lcall <address 16>     ; stack ← PC  
                        ; PC ← address 16 bit
```

Return

- Return is also similar to a jump, but
 - Return instruction **pops PC** from stack to get address to jump to

ret

; PC ← stack

Initializing Stack Pointer

- SP is initialized to 07 after reset.(Same address as R7)
- With each push operation 1st , pc is increased
- When using subroutines, the stack will be used to store the PC, so it is very important to initialize the stack pointer. Location **2Fh** is often used.

```
mov SP, #2Fh
```

Why Subroutines?

- Subroutines allow us to have "**structured**" assembly language programs.
- This is useful for breaking a large design into manageable parts.
- It **saves code space** when subroutines can be called many times in the same program.

example of delay

```
    mov a,#0aah
Back1:mov p0,a
    lcall delay1
    cpl a
    sjmp back1
Delay1:mov r0,#0ffh;1cycle
Here:  djnz r0,here ;2cycle
    ret          ;2cycle
    end
```

Delay=1+255*2+2=513 cycle

Delay2:

```
    mov r6,#0ffh
back1: mov r7,#0ffh ;1cycle
Here:  djnz r7,here ;2cycle
    djnz r6,back1;2cycle
    ret          ;2cycle
    end
```

Delay=1+(1+255*2+2)*255+2
=130818 machine cycle